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Scope Statement: This commentary addresses the prescient issue of blame culture and its serious welfare implications for veterinarians. It details how a drug manufacturer has attempted to deflect blame for high adverse event rates associated with one of its best-selling products by unjustifiably questioning the clinical judgment of veterinarians. Authored by experts with no financial conflicts of interest, this evidence-based commentary challenges misleading claims regarding bedinvetmab (Beransa or Librela) and defends the core principle of open and honest reporting.

Musculoskeletal Adverse Events in Dogs Receiving Bedinvetmab (Librela): A Response to Misleading Claims

Musculoskeletal adverse events in dogs receiving bedinvetmab (Librela) challenged the premise that severe side-effects of nerve growth factor (NGF) suppression seen in humans would not translate to companion animals (1). In principle, this research should have triggered a significant re-evaluation of the drug's benefit-risk profile by the manufacturer, prompting stringent patient selection criteria and more robust, transparent pharmacovigilance. In practice, Zoetis vilified and trivialized the research (2), forcing us to contextualize their false and misleading claims.

A central tactic is the deflection of blame, exemplified by Zoetis labelling reports for dogs receiving the recommended dose as 'overdoses' (1). While manufacturers are responsible for *product* safety, clinicians must ensure *therapy* safety and communicate risk to caregivers. With escalating depression and suicide rates (3), misplaced criticism of veterinarians must be taken seriously. Deflecting blame onto veterinarians exposes them to baseless public criticism for 'concealing' risks when, in reality, they are merely relaying the company's own biased guidance. In effect, the manufacturer is compromising the reputation of local veterinarians to protect its product.

In December 2024, the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) issued a formal safety warning for Librela (bedinvetmab) after identifying disproportionately high adverse event reports compared with other OA drugs (4). Statistically significant safety signals included:

- **Neurological:** focal seizures (41x higher risk), epileptic seizures (13x), encephalitis (8x), neuromuscular disorders (8x), impaired consciousness (7x).
- **Musculoskeletal:** osteosarcoma (5x), musculoskeletal disorders (4x), lameness (3x).

- **Others:** collapse (4x), syncope (4x), polyuria (4x).

Zoetis responded to the FDA's "Dear Veterinarian" letter by claiming it was not a "warning" and contained "no new public data" (5). Both claims are misleading. A formal alert from a regulator detailing high rates of serious events is, by definition, a warning. Moreover, raw data becomes meaningful *new* information only after expert analysis—the very service the FDA provided.

Zoetis deflected blame onto veterinary professionals by suggesting the high adverse event rate was fuelled by social media-driven "over-reporting" (4). This accusation questions the professional judgment of our community, as 89% of reports were filed by healthcare professionals. This pattern of questioning veterinarians' clinical acumen continued in their response to the FDA's safety signal for ataxia—a distinctive uncoordinated gait. Despite the straightforward clinical distinction between ataxia and weakness from osteoarthritis, Zoetis suggested veterinarians were misinterpreting the two—a baseless claim that casts aspersions on our core clinical skills (6).

While Zoetis was critical of veterinary professionals, the FDA was critical of Zoetis, having twice cited the company for misbranding Librela with misleading promotional materials. The first warning letter concerned the misrepresentation of clinical trial data on its professional website to create a misleading impression of Librela's efficacy (7). The second concerned promotional videos that created a "misleading impression regarding the safety" of Librela because risks were not presented with "a prominence and accessibility comparable to the benefits" (8).

Zoetis, in turn, has consistently criticized independent researchers (Table 1), authoring two letters dismissing safety concerns (13-14), and formally demanding the retraction of a critical evidence analysis (15)¹. Simultaneously, Zoetis's own paid consultants are conducting internal drug safety

investigations, creating an untenable paradox: the same entity working to downplay safety concerns is positioned as the only qualified investigator.

This strategy exploits a critical information gap. Reading all relevant published research is impossible, so many veterinarians will be unaware that Zoetis's criticisms are unfounded. Zoetis capitalized on this by issuing their rebuttals in a promotional flyer (2)—a format exempt from impartial, expert fact-checking. The biased information landscape is compounded by the fact that 6/9 specialists on a high-profile expert panel that recommended Librela as first-line therapy for mild osteoarthritis declared financial ties to Zoetis (16).

Regulators must make high-stakes decisions based on incomplete or conflicting data, a challenge aggravated by intense media coverage and pressure from those with financial interests in the outcome. Such conditions demand expert judgment in circumstances where randomized controlled trials would be unethical or impractical, events are emergent, or immediate safety decisions are required (12). Yet, history shows that necessary interventions are often deferred in the absence of 'solid' evidence, with devastating consequences (17).

The opioid crisis is a tragic example with stark parallels to the current situation. Like Librela, OxyContin was a popular and effective painkiller, with over 14 million prescriptions dispensed in only two years (18). But its blockbuster status was enabled by systemic failures in post-marketing pharmacovigilance. Years passed before a causal link to addiction and overdose was established—a delay that ultimately cost over 100,000 lives (19).

The opioid crisis provides a worrying example of the 'denominator fallacy': using massive sales figures to downplay risk. In 2012, enough opioid prescriptions were dispensed for every adult in the

USA to have a bottle of pills (18), resulting in 16,007 deaths (19). Using sales figures as a denominator results in a mortality rate of 0.006%, dramatically obscuring the true scale of the crisis.

Zoetis persistently leverages the denominator fallacy with Librela—counting monthly doses sold rather than individual patients treated—and its misleading effect is magnified by the extreme scale of under-reporting in veterinary pharmacovigilance. For example, the clinical incidence of gastrointestinal side effects for the NSAID carprofen is ~5%, yet a large-scale pharmacovigilance study found a *reported* rate of only 0.013% (20). This 385-fold discrepancy between reality and reported data illustrates the magnitude of the problem.

This massive evidence-practice gap exposes Zoetis's misleading safety claims. Applying a 385-fold correction means events they classify as 'rare' become 'common' (6). The discrepancy is even starker for efficacy: the post-marketing lack of efficacy rate is only 0.02% (6), while pre-marketing trials found a ~40% non-response rate (21, 22). This 2,000-fold difference highlights the profound unreliability of using uncorrected pharmacovigilance data to portray a drug's risk-benefit profile.

The veterinary profession has unique access to a powerful drug class deemed too risky for human use. This privilege comes with a profound responsibility to respect emerging safety signals.

Ultimately, independent experts and caregivers are not responsible for proving a drug is safe or unsafe. That responsibility lies with the manufacturer, who must *prove* that new safety signals are *not* a cause for concern. Attacking the sources of safety signals with misleading promotional materials is *not* a substitute for transparent evidence; it is an abdication of that core responsibility.

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Footnote

¹The retraction demand concerned a 2023 critical appraisal by Dr. Kronenberger (15). The existence of this unpublished letter was confirmed by personal communication with the author (K. Kronenberger, personal communication, 30 August 2025).

Disputed Claim	Verifiable Facts
Non-equivalent datasets were used to compare Librela's adverse event reports to six comparator drugs [2].	Farrell et al's primary hypothesis was that Librela's MSAER rate would not exceed that of comparator drugs by more than 50%. The primary analysis was anchored from Librela's release in February 2021, ensuring a direct, like-for-like comparison over the exact same time period [1].
The absence of product data in the EudraVigilance database before 2004 was a "major limitation" [2].	This criticism diverts attention from the study's primary finding: a 9-fold higher reporting rate of serious musculoskeletal adverse events for Librela compared to six other OA medications in the <i>post-marketing period (2021-2024)</i> . The study's secondary analysis correctly began in 2004 because new EU legislation that year mandated the electronic reporting of adverse events, making it the most relevant start date for comparing new drug launches including Previcox® (2004), Onsior® (2008), Galliprant® (2018), and Daxocox® (2021) [1].
The qualitative analysis used to exclude confounding diagnoses "has never been reported and is not referenced" [2].	Qualitative (i.e. descriptive) disproportionality analysis prevented a dramatic overestimation of Librela's risks. Without it, inclusion of confounding cases would have created a spurious, nearly five-fold increase in reported adverse events. A combined quantitative-qualitative method is a cornerstone of risk analysis, as illustrated by the investigation of cigarettes and lung cancer [9], thalidomide and birth defects [10], and many others.
The 19 dogs reviewed by the expert panel resulted from "global solicitation of cases" and was compromised by "selection bias" [2].	This allegation is unfounded. As stated in the manuscript, the 19 adjudicated dogs were the product of spontaneous reporting <i>without any call for cases</i> . This process is a classic example of signal detection in pharmacovigilance and is fundamentally different from the systematic, non-random subject selection that defines selection bias [1].
Zoetis compared the 19 adjudicated cases to the millions of Librela doses sold globally [2].	Pharmacovigilance principles, established by CIOMS [11] and employed by the FDA and EMA [12], confirm this approach, termed 'the denominator fallacy', is seriously misleading because it ignores the fundamental problem of under-reporting. The valid scientific method is disproportionality analysis.
Zoetis's promotional flyer included the statement: "Allowing our patients to remain in pain is not an option" [2].	This statement creates a false dichotomy, incorrectly framing a call for vigilance as a choice to let animals suffer. Farrell et al. did <i>not</i> advocate withholding treatment, but rather ensuring <i>informed consent</i> , concluding that "further investigation and close clinical monitoring... are warranted" [1]. Advocating for caregiver awareness of potential risks is a cornerstone of ethical veterinary practice and is fundamentally different from advocating that pets "remain in pain."
EU: European Union, FDA: Food and Drug Administration, EMA: European Medicines Agency, CIOMS: Council for International Organizations of Medical Sciences, MSAER: Musculoskeletal adverse event report	

Table 1: Disputed claims made by Zoetis regarding the methodology of the Farrell et al. study (1), with corresponding evidence-based rebuttals.